

The Effects of the Institutional Practices on Students' academic Writing in Moroccan EFL classes: Allal El Fassi High school As a Case Study

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Abstract:

This study seeks to explore the challenges EFL and ESL Moroccan high school students face in academic writing. Writing, among the four skills, plays a crucial role in language production. Yet, students often avoid writing tasks because they fail to produce powerful written products. The purpose of this study is to highlight the factors affecting students' writing skills and suggesting measures on how to help them achieve a level of proficiency in written production. The research paper was conducted based on survey questionnaires, classroom observations and writing samples. The findings reveal that the common difficulties students encounter in writing are L1 transfer, lack of practice, poor repertoire of vocabulary and insufficient knowledge input. These difficulties are also affected by several variables such as the poor institutional practices of teaching writing, students' lack of interest and their attitudes towards writing skills. Utilizing powerful pedagogical ground based on positive feedback, daily

class report writings, self or peer reflection and analysing students' needs are measures recommended assisting learners to overcome their writing challenges.

Keywords:

Reflection, needs analysis, institutional practices, feedback, academic writing

Introduction:

Many research studies have argued the challenges EFL and ESL learners face in writing skills because of their complex nature. The complexity lies in conveying meaningful sentences. Nunan (1989) argues that writing is an extremely difficult cognitive activity which requires the learner to have control over various factors. These factors vary from academic background and personal interest of the writer to various psychological, linguistic and cognitive phenomena. The academic failure or success is often counted on the power of writing. Both high school learners and teachers endure a great deal because of the poor outcomes of writing skills. This often instils a kind of frustration on the part of students who tend to avoid writing as it is so daunting a task to carry out. Most often, students lose the point to write a powerful piece of writing when there is a mismatch of the underlined with the intended goals of teaching and learning writing. Students need to write with a purpose and an audience in mind. This helps learners to plan their writing appropriately. Learners start writing the moment they are given the topic. That is, they do not take enough time to plan their written texts. This learning habit affects their ability to produce rich texts, which can encourage them to gain confidence and improve their writing skills

The institutional practices and students' attitudes towards the complex nature of writing appear to be determining factors in the progress of

communicative language teaching and learning. From my own experience as a teacher, students' interest in learning to write is either given little importance or ignored altogether. Written tasks are always scheduled at the end of textbooks' units. That is, students are not given enough opportunities to assimilate the repertoire of vocabulary and structures to which they are exposed in classes. They get accustomed to writing occasionally. Therefore, they perceive writing skill as it is not important for language learning. Also, the topics, which textbook activities assign, do not attend to students' needs. Therefore, students attempt to avoid writing skills since they feel afraid of making mistakes. Their strong apprehension affects their ability to express their thoughts freely and lose confidence. More importantly, writing tasks do not provide them enough time to develop their cognitive abilities. Consequently, when they come to write, they forget if they have written before. They are not regularly acquainted with the genres of texts they are to produce. They do not attempt to write creatively and develop their potentials of writing skills, but they simply write as they have to finish written tasks. The apprehension generated from stress does not leave time for learners to build up their written product appropriately. It rather leads learners to learn poor writing habits. Without doubt, writing skill is very important in language learning. As a consequence, the present study was implemented to acknowledge the importance of reflection, or reflective practice, in writing along with daily report writings, in improving writing skills in EFL Moroccan High school classes.

Literature Review:

Several studies have emphasized the most crucial role of writing in language learning. Harmer (1998) stated “ the reasons for teaching writing to students of English as a foreign language include reinforcement, language

development, learning style, and most importantly, writing as a skill in its own right". Therefore, it has become necessary for learners to master writing skills to communicate their ideas. It is not as easy as one might think. It needs careful planning that is mapped over many stages to produce coherent and cohesive texts. That is why; it is a complex and challenging cognitive ability. According to Nunan (1989) indicated that writing is the most complicated and challenging skill to learn for those who learn English as a foreign language because "writing is a highly complex, cognitive ability for all in which the writer is required to demonstrate several of variables simultaneously". Following this line, learners do not have other alternative than that of taking control over writing skill to achieve the goal of language learning. Additionally, Kern (2000) believes that writing is an active process requiring active thinking and problem solving. That is the writer has to make a connection between the schemata and the new elements to create new knowledge structures. Yet, this creativity would not take place unless cultural knowledge of the society addressed is acquired. Learners need to compare between past and present experiences to effectively gain insights towards reflecting on their learning habits.

Writers assume a big responsibility lies behind conveying comprehensible ideas that paves the way for readers to encode appropriate meanings. Nunan (2003) defines "writing as both physical and mental act. At the most basic level, writing is the physical act of communicating words or ideas to some medium. On the other hand, writing is the mental work of inventing ideas, thinking about how to express them and organizing them into statements and paragraphs they will be clear to a reader". So, language comprehension is achieved unless it involves meaningful segments of language: words, sentences and structures. As a matter of fact, learning language regulations is of paramount importance in taking risks for producing meaningful content. A study showed that the ability to write is not an option but a necessity, or obligation for everyone

(Alliance, 6); improving language learning is counted on writing because writing often helps learners to develop ideas or thoughts (Watson, 2001). Following the same line of thinking, writing is meant to be a kind of art in language teaching and learning in which learners creatively produce infinite number of structures. Yet, they should have already been equipped with a rich input which they can learn through exposure. Lack of linguistic repertoire contributes to students' withdrawal from writing. As they venture to write based on their L1 input, they certainly produce poor ideas that are most often awkward.

Most research studies have been concerned with writing since the ultimate goal of EFL or ESL learning is communication. So, writing has begun to gain popularity in all over the world as it provides an added value to language learning. **For many years, writing has become a pillar in foreign language teaching. Unlike writing in an L1, writing in an L2 or FL is quite a challenging. It requires an attainment of sufficient linguistic proficiency (Hinkel, 2004).** Attention is focused on the importance of reflection in teaching and learning, notably written production. Many scholars consider reflection as a vital pedagogical tool that serves to reflect on past experiences and make use of them to improve and remedy writing skills. In one way or another, comparing present and past experiences often develop insights on how to achieve a successful learning experience. according to **John Dewey (1933), an American psychologist, philosopher and educational reformer believed that reflection is a key ingredient to forming deeper connectors with experience, defining it as “ Active, persistent, and careful consideration of any belief or supposed form of knowledge in the light of the grounds that support it and the further conclusions to which it tends”(p.9).** Reflection is an outstanding pedagogical tool which can generate its power from daily writing practice , self and peer reflection.

Adopting these remedial assets, students can assess and evaluate their own written products and that of their peers.

Many scholars have argued the efficiency of reflective teaching in the light of writing journals and portfolios. Learners are hardly familiar with these interesting projects. Time constraints and students' attitudes have a significant impact on their willingness to explore their writing abilities. Most students show negative attitudes towards writing. Actually, they may demonstrate control over other language skills, but they are to face difficulties when they are asked to write. Differently put, they have the fear of making writing mistakes. Therefore, they do not explore their knowledge of writing and express their thoughts. Thus, Erkan and Saban (2011) maintained that "success with writing in a foreign language may be related to attitudes towards writing, apprehension about writing, and self-efficacy in writing" (p. 168). For this reason, we have to encourage learners through asking them to report the teaching items during each session. This will certainly motivate them to be attentive and revise lessons on a regular basis through writing reports. In doing so, learners have enough time to practice writing and teachers can evaluate the efficiency of their pedagogical practices and the extent to how successful they are. Reports writing leads towards professional development as well as autonomous learning. Learners write using the rich input given during class sessions. In this case, they are to attend to their needs as they are eagerly motivated to write concerning what they are much more interested in. More importantly, they exploit the teaching items and enrich their repertoire of vocabulary as well. Students always ignore writing skills because they do not have enough input which bestows on them the ability to explore their meta-cognitive abilities.

Methods and data:

In this scientific research paper, the study adopted a qualitative approach to investigate students' writing challenges, factors affecting their writing progress, and suggestions to improve EFL/ESL Moroccan intermediate learners. Two online questionnaires were conducted for both teachers and students. The questions were developed in the context of reflective practice. They seek to touch up on the challenges EFL teachers and students face at the level of written production. That is to say, they serve to measure the extent to which students enhance their writing skills counted on daily classroom reports and reflection. The reports were written based on the given teaching items. In doing so, students are given enough time to practice their writing skills as teachers are provided with enough data to judge the mean gaps meant to affect students' writing products. Simultaneously, students benefit from abundant opportunities to practice writing skills. In a similar vein, the study investigates the poor institutional practices which impact writing progress. Likewise, interviews were administered to twenty intermediate students from different classes to get direct feedback about the challenges they face in writing skills. It provides insights on the challenges of writing so that we can help students overcome their challenges and improve their writing skills.

All the questions address the poor writing skills that affect the progress of language learning, notably in academic writing. Several techniques of data collection, questionnaires, interviews and reports writing, are used to find out the main difficulties faced by EFL and ESL students while they come to produce written texts. In one way or another, we attempt to involve both teachers and students to evaluate the power of the teaching methodology. There are many pedagogical variables intertwined to develop poor learning habits, which students develop under the socio-cultural contexts and the philosophy of the pedagogical ground. The teaching methodologies and materials used hardly correspond to students' needs.

The amalgam questions try to uncover the most difficulties face students in writing from different perspectives in order that we can be able to seek pertinent solutions. Solutions best suit to fill the gap other scientific researchers fail to help learners improve their writing skills as students and teachers still complain about the complex nature of writing that render poor writing skills.

Analysis and results:

The data collected includes interviews about the common challenges EFL students in Allal Elle Fassi high school face in writing skills. The findings revealed the following results:

Participant 1 commented “most of the times, I fail to find the exact words to express my thoughts. Therefore, I always resort to my L1 and translate referring to “google traduction”.

Participant 2 said “some students are reluctant to write because they are afraid of making mistakes”

Participant 3 noted “we find it challenging to appropriately place mechanics of writing as they are important for coherence and cohesion”

Participant 4 stated “lack of ideas along with topics of little interest do not motivate students to engage in writing activities”

Participant 5 added “we do not regularly receive any kind of feedback from our teachers. As a result, we avoid writing tasks because we do not have the opportunity to measure our progress to get motivated”

Participant 6 “ teachers do not guide or model writing samples during classes, but writing activities are usually assigned as homework”

Participant 7 declared “I believe that writing challenges are related to the time allocated to writing practice, which is very limited. Student could progress through making mistakes and learning from them”

In the light of the findings, the institutional practices and materials used contribute to students’ poor writing habits. They do not seem to help learners develop their writing abilities as they fail successively to take risks in writing good quality texts. Also, students hardly practice writing activities or keep records to measure their progress. They only preserve to finish writing tasks, but they are indifferent about the quality of writing produced. The writing challenges are often aggravated when students do not attempt to communicate them to their teachers. Other times, the tools used to test students’ writing skills and teachers’ methodology of teaching impact the quality of students’ written products. Yet, it is viewed that practice plays an essential ingredient in improving writing skills. Reporting classroom session as instrument supported in the guise of reflection serves as key factor towards enhancing students’ writing skills. Students are accustomed to developing good habits of writing daily in which teachers as the masters reflect and evaluate their writing as they gradually grow and achieve a level of control over writing. Students avoid the fear of writing because they write regularly without apprehension of making mistakes on writing. After one month of report writings practice, there was a remarkable change as I observe that students start to develop and gain confidence. They become able of producing infinite number of structures.

Students feel more encouraged to write if they are given the opportunity to choose issues that attend to their needs,. On the contrary, they unwillingly write when they write on topics imposed on them. In this case, they write to merely complete the assigned task. Therefore, they usually refer to their L1 to solve the problem and write no matter what quality of writing. Without doubt, reflective

practice creates wonders because both teachers and students engage to assess the quality of teaching and learning. Teachers seek professional development based on students' reflection. Likewise, students benefit from their own feedback and that of teachers. Put in a nutshell, reporting classroom sessions daily leads students to perceive that writing is the most important skill among the other skills of language learning. In doing so, students will become aware of the role of writing in academic success and they will not avoid writing tasks anymore. Additionally, teachers should be ready to use the best pedagogical tools to assist students to change their standpoints towards writing and making it fun loving activity. EFL or ESL students like to study English as they are eager to communicate. It is easy to engage them in different writing genres and make them feel the progress taking place. Keeping reports writing and turning to them every now and then will encourage students to compare and check their level of progress. In short, students have potentials to explore but teachers should be there to help them make use of their cognitive and meta-cognitive abilities. Practice with reflection serve to perfectly assist learners to be motivated to write, but they still have problems with the appropriate use of mechanics in writing.

Discussion:

The study conducted showed that EFL Moroccan High school students in Allan ElFassi face a number of challenges while they are asked to write. Lack of practice, lack of ideas, L1 transfer, students' attitudes, feedback, poor linguistic repertoire, misuse of mechanics of writing are factors affecting students' progress in writing. The study aims at seeking remedial measures to help learners improve their writing skills. Class writing reports and reflection were suggested to provide students enough time to freely practice writing skills. Reports writings are not graded or taken as part of students' evaluation for academic success. It is a free

activity in which students do not work under stress. To evaluate the effectiveness of report writing activity, several classes were asked to write reports in every session for nearly one month. At the very outset, students felt unmotivated to write because they were not accustomed to writing. A case in point, in 2nd year baccalaureate textbooks, writing activities were always left till the end of the units. For this reason, students hold the belief that writing skills are left till the end of textbooks' units since they are not as important as the other skills. So, students either write some or none. They ignore the vital prominence of writing in academic success. Writing is a key factor towards students' academic success. Before embarking on this tool of training, I tried to argue the importance of practice in overcoming the challenges students face while writing. So, they get encouraged to handle writing tasks and get rid of the apprehension they have which often leads to poor writing habits or failure, if I may say so.

Daily writing activities assist learners to sense a good level of progress in writing skills despite their mistakes. In the first stages, the feedback was mainly given on the content as counted on motivating students to practice writing. In other words, it provides them with the floor to self-correct and learn from their mistakes. Students, on their part, feel inspired to refer to present and past experiences to reflect on their written texts. That is to say, they make great efforts to assimilate words they learn during classes and they set forth to demonstrate high ability to use them in writing skills. Following the same line of thinking, they gradually accumulate a rich repertoire of vocabulary that helps them to write infinite structures as they develop daily. They often refer to their past experiences to measure the extent of their improvement. This, in return, makes them feel confident for they attain an outstanding level of writing performance. Actually, most of students' present writing texts seem to see light and gain ground over past experiences. Writing progress is achieved based on reflective practice and above all practice makes perfect as known. On the other hand, time constraints impact students'

quality of writing. Hence, practice is implemented in the light of reflection so that students can facilitate their writing habits and suffice the end goal of EFL and ESL learning.

All the above arguments lead us to present Krashen's "input hypothesis" that argues the importance of students' background knowledge. In a sense, teachers need to equip their students with rich input before they ask them to write. For example, teachers may take some time to explore the topic issued so that students can have some ideas to develop. That is why, when students are exposed to rich content of ideas, they feel more comfortable in writing. Clearly put, learners with rich input have abundant opportunities to explore their abilities and write creatively. However, students may leave a considerable gap between theory and practice. That is to say, they come to learn infinite set of English knowledge repertoire every day, but they rarely put it into practice. It is generally believed that practice makes perfect. The more students practice writing, the easier it becomes. For this reason, we need to give our students enough time to practice writing to become successful writers.

It is undeniable that writing is precious moments where students demonstrate the items being taught and assess the extent of their mastery of language. In this respect, students need appropriate guidance that boosts their writing philosophy. We may give them indirect feedbacks that do not create a kind of apprehension of writing. In doing so, students independently correct their mistakes following teachers' guidelines. Our underlying objective is to motivate students to become agents in their own learning and follow the learner-centeredness approach to learning writing. Motivation incentive is raised to the maximum as students adopt constructive method to composing as the masters of their own written products.

Conclusion:

In Most Moroccan EFL classes, writing remains the most difficult skill in language learning. Yet, many scholars tried hard to compensate for the gaps left in this area. Writing is still a challenging task for both teachers and learners because they do not give it much importance though it is viewed a key factor towards achieving academic success. the ultimate goal of language learning is communication or language production. Therefore, I strongly believe the “comprehensible input hypothesis” of Krashen seems essential for learners to gain rich linguistic repertoire of language through constructive practice. In a sense, learning involves conscious knowledge of language rules through formal instructions. Conscious learning also plays an important role in language production by checking and editing utterances. Furthermore, Krashen argues that language learners improve their linguistic competence when language used in class is adapted to students’ level. They master ability to produce language as they receive comprehensible input. Therefore, teachers have to use simple and comprehensible language in order to assist students build their internal linguistic competence. As a result, reporting classroom sessions is an opportunity for students to exploit language used in class for writing tasks. Students can be motivated to write as the learning environment is provided by rich input. This may be an effective teaching tool for students to foster their writing skills. We need regularly to train students on writing freely away from all kinds of stress. This philosophy of improving writing helps that much in exploring creativity which may not surface if students are working under stress.

More importantly, students feel a complex of inferiority as they rarely write on topics of their interest. Therefore, they do not feel motivated to produce a given text. Instead, they avoid writing tasks because they are afraid of

producing poor quality of writing. As a consequence, it is of great importance that we always need to put students at the core of the teaching and learning process. That is to say, we are to foreground the floor for students to demonstrate creativity in a more relaxed atmosphere. Simply put, extrinsic motivation is to surface if students carry out activities they enjoy. Furthermore, students will be encouraged to write regularly as they will embrace practice as key towards obtaining proficiency level in writing. We need to give our students enough time to practice writing activities to do away with the complex fear they have towards writing. To add more, teachers are to opt for appropriate strategies of correcting students' writing. It needs to foster students' autonomous learning grounded so that they can integrate reflection to improve reflective writing. To offer enough time for students to judge the quality of their writing, we had better encourage reflective practice as the best teaching and learning tool in preparing influential writers.

The assessing criteria will be collecting students' class reports in the form of a portfolio-like in which they are to refer to in order that they can measure the extent of their progress. If they attain remarkable progress, they will certainly be confident and liable to create infinite structures they have never written before. They will boost their self-esteem and take risks in producing good quality texts. Most of the students consider writing as a minor activity which does need much importance. This attitude is generated on the part of students due to the poor time provided to writing activities in EFL Moroccan classes. Writing tasks are usually assigned once at the end of each teaching unit. As a consequence, I, as a teacher, would say that writing skills are either given little time or ignored altogether. Writing should be continuously practiced in order to give students enough time to exploit the most teaching items and make students believe that writing is the most fundamental skill in language learning. Without writing skill, students will not make any progress in language learning because it is the cornerstone of

communication, the end mean of language learning in which students try hard to reach a level of proficiency

The present survey was collected and analyzed adopting a qualitative descriptive approach. Based on the findings, the following suggestions are made:

- Writing daily reports based on the teaching items as a strategy to train students on writing regularly.
- Providing abundant opportunities for learners to write on different genres.
- Encouraging peer and group work. Students have chances to exchange their pieces of writing and benefit from each other.
- Integrating self and peer reflection in writing activities.
- Providing writing sample before assigning writing activities.
- Giving positive and regular feedback for students to evaluate their progress.
- Opting for best strategies that attend to students' level and needs to teach writing skills.

Undoubtedly, class writing reports, self and peer reflection were used by the researcher to handle the challenges faced in writing skills. As a consequence, the survey may be used in the future by other researchers. In other words, they may alternatively use another tool for data analysis that could produce some reliable findings. In fact, the time allotted for writing practice and students' reflection on their pieces of writing is enough to judge the effectiveness of reports writing in the context of reflection. A larger study with enough time and a large number of participants from different levels would produce appealing findings. A study on the context of ICT (Information Communication Technology) in reflective practice may recall some good orientations on how to improve writing skills.

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